

THE EVOLUTION OF SPEAKING SKILLS BY FACILITATING INTERACTION AND THE IMPORTANCE OF SPEAKING ABILITIES

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Abstract: Achieving oral communication has become the focus and ultimate goal of the second language learning and teaching process. However, the students do not have enough opportunities to interact in the classroom which can greatly help them develop their speaking skills. In this article, I will try to give some suggestions for students. In order to carry out this project, the qualitative methodology will be used to gather data through classroom observations and the use of oral activities such as simulations, jigsaw and story completion activities. The findings of this research should provide valuable information regarding the effect of using oral activities that involve interaction to develop student's speaking skills.

Key words: oral communication, interaction, speaking skills, methodological limitations, simulations, story completion, jigsaw, strategic competence, production skills, types of speaking, interpersonal skills.

OG'ZAKI NUTQ QOBILIYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH EVOLYUTSIYASI VA NUTQ QOBILIYATLARINING MUHIM AHAMIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Og'zaki muloqotga erishish ikkinchi tilni o'rganish va o'qitish jarayonining asosiy maqsadi va yakuniy maqsadiga aylanmoqda. Biroq, talabalar sinfda muloqot qilish uchun etarli imkoniyatlarga ega emaslar, bu ularning nutq qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga katta yordam beradi. Ushbu maqolada men yosh o'quvchilar va talabalar uchun ham ba'zi bilgan tavsiyalarimni berishga harakat qilaman. Ushbu loyihani amalga oshirish uchun sinfda kuzatishlar va simulyatsiya, jigsa (puzzle-rasmi boshqotirma) va hikoyani yakunlash kabi og'zaki faoliyatdan foydalanish orqali ma'lumotlarni to'plash uchun sifatli metodologiya qo'llaniladi. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari talabalarning nutq qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun o'zaro ta'sirni o'z ichiga olgan og'zaki faoliyatdan foydalanish ta'siri haqida qimmatli ma'lumotlarni taqdim etishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: og'zaki muloqot, o'zaro ta'sir, nutq qobiliyatlari, uslubiy cheklovlar, simulyatsiya, hikoyani yakunlash, jigso, strategik kompetentsiya, ishlab chiqarish ko'nikmalari, nutq turlari, shaxslararo munosabatlar.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the communicative approach caused a big impact in the analysis of foreign language teaching goals leading to changes in language teaching worldwide within which the attention to oral interaction of importance. Nevertheless, as ESL students with

pedagogical experience at schools and English language academies, we have seen that learners usually have difficulties with their speaking skills. Some of the reasons are that teachers are not aware that the idea of classroom interaction is vital importance to second language learning due to the opportunities it creates to improve knowledge and speaking skills. Also, students do not have enough opportunities in the classroom to be put in real life situations in which they can practice and express their own thoughts. As a result, students cannot develop fluency and improve their overall levels of communication. For this reason, we considered it necessary to incorporate classroom activities that involve interaction to help students develop their speaking skills. Moreover, I can cite various forms as an example of the development of oral communication.

Interaction

“Interaction is the collaborative exchange of thoughts, feelings or ideas between two or more people, resulting in a reciprocal effect on each other”. In this sense, through the use of interaction, students have the opportunity to express their own ideas, views, opinions, thoughts and feelings in real communicative.

Speaking Skill

“The speaking is the productive oral skill. It consists of producing systematic verbal utterance to convey meaning”. Speaking is the ability that enables us to communicate and to exchange our ideas effectively.

Interpersonal skill

The success of the implementation of the jigsaw technique in the classroom depends on students ‘social skills including leadership, decision-making, trust-building, communication, conflict-management skills among others.

Types of speaking

Imitative: this type of speaking refers to the practice of a word regarding the intonation in order to focus on a specific component of the language form. In other words, this is the repetition of a word or a sentence whose principal aim is pronunciation.

Intensive: it is used to practice phonological and grammatical aspects of language. It can be carried out through the use of group work for instance story completion in which each student has to give some sentences in order to complete a story.

Responsive: an important aspect of this type of speaking is interaction between teachers and students or students using questions or comments as a way to initiate a short conversation but the answers are very limited and do not turn into dialogues. The language that is produced is sometimes meaningful and authentic.

Simulations

“A simulation is to act out a pretend real-life encounter between learners as though it were actually happening”. For example, acting out a job interview, a meeting on an airplane or a business conference. This encourage oral fluency as the learners would behave as those characters would, probably expressing thoughts and feelings that they do not necessarily agree with.

THE RESEARCH METHOD

In order to fulfill the objectives of this project, it is necessary to follow a set of steps which will be developed in this chapter. This includes the design, sample, setting and validation criteria. Besides, the instruments used to get the information will be described, as well as the

procedure that will be developed in the research process. The objectives of this research method are: to describe facts; to formulate hypothesis, to make a descriptive diagnosis of specific phenomena and to comprehend the relationship and social interactions. I selected this paradigm due to the fact that we will analyze, interpret and make a detailed description of a situation by applying our techniques to develop learners speaking skills by facilitating interaction.

For the development our project we will use action which belongs to the qualitative research. Kemmis says “ Action research is a form of self-reflective enquiry undertaken by participants in social (including educational) situations in order to improve the rationality and the justice of (a) their own social or educational practices, (b) the understanding of these practices and (c) the situations in which the practices are carried out. In other words, action research is a process that involves action, reflection and observation of a social issue aimed at improving the understanding and methods involved in education thus, contributing to the development of the pedagogical practices. In addition, Parsons and Brown state that action research is designed especially for teachers as a way to obtain information with the purpose of improving teaching practices or giving solution to different problems that can appear in the classroom. It can be carried out through the use of observations and the collection of information that can be useful for the researcher to reflect and decide what strategies are more suitable to apply in the classroom so students have a good experience in their learning process.

Through the use of observations and activities used to gather the information we might find problems related to the lack of interest and reluctance on the part of the students and teachers to collaborate with us, which can make it difficult to obtain satisfying results when analyzing the information.

We think that the techniques that we are going to apply will be useful to determine if the activities that we will develop with the students will have an effect and will show an improvement and progress in their performance when using the foreign language.

Therefore, this type of research will be used to address the problem identified, design a plan to improve our teaching practices by facilitating and fostering interaction to develop the speaking skills, observe the process which will provide new insights and reflect upon the possible constraints and benefits concerning the goals of the teaching and learning environment.

Significance of the study

According to my experience learning English as a foreign language, I have realized that students do indeed have difficulties communicating and they struggle when it comes to expressing their thoughts and opinions in the foreign language.

This project has a methodological and practical importance. In terms of methodological importance, we propose to implement communicative activities that involve interaction in order to foster students’ speaking skill. In terms of practical importance, we intend to contribute to the solution of the problem that students experience since they do not have enough opportunities to interact in the language they are learning.

In addition, this research has a relevant importance for teachers and students. For teachers because it can provide them with new techniques, strategies and communicative activities that involve social interaction to facilitate the teaching and learning process.

Furthermore, my research can help students produce and understand language more effectively.

Speaking in a second language has always had an important place through the history of the language teaching and learning and in the last decades it has become the focus of the teaching process leaving aside the conventional methods that only had a structural focus. In addition, a lot has been written about the speaking skill, and several authors have provided different definitions about it.

According to Chaney, the speaking is a mechanism of constructing and sharing meaning by using verbal and non-verbal symbols in different situations.

In relation to Chaney states that, “speaking is an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing and receiving and processing information”. In this sense, speaking is a way to interact with each other people exchanging information and alternating the role as listener as well as speaker in order to express ideas and transmit meaning.

Using group work and pair work

Pair work and group work activities can be used during the process of learning in order to increase the amount of time that learners get to practice the target language. Teachers should limit the amount of time they talk and act as facilitators asking questions and offering clarification so students have more time to interact themselves using the language.

Today is widely known that the most important goal to be reached in the EFL teaching and learning process is communication and interaction plays an essential role in it.

In this sense, some theories support the idea that interaction enables the development of first and second language acquisition. Therefore, in order to reach a meaningful learning outcome, students need to be provided with opportunities to interact in the classroom and teachers must encourage them to share ideas, opinions and thoughts because it is a good way to make them active rather than passive participants.

In this section, we will analyze the information collected during the research process through the application of classroom observation, recordings and the use of oral activities such as simulations and the interactions. The techniques used to gather the information will be also described, analyzed and interpreted.

I think that my work is a valid since the techniques I selected will measure the factor that I intend to measure that is the effect of interaction to develop the speaking skill.

In addition, I consider that my work will be reliable because we will use the pilot study which will give a consistent support to the effectiveness of our instruments.

My techniques will be proved with 10 learners through the pilot study which will help us realize possible difficulties we will face in the development of my investigation in order to overcome them.

Foreign students in English-speaking countries

Foreign students as percentage of total student number

	2004	2012
USA	2%	2%
UK	9%	13%
Australia	19%	24%
Canada	5%	7%

In the above table, I have tried to show the education of students studying in countries where English is the main language. This indicator was about 180 people in the United States in 2004, and by 2012, these numbers were close to 250 people. In the United Kingdom, around 130 students have increased to 200 by 2012. In Australia, however, the numbers start at the same level as the UK, with a share of around 200 foreign students in 2012. In Canada, you can see that these numbers are much lower.

Through these statistics, mainly I want to improve the English speaking capacity among young people and teenagers, because most of the young people today, continue their studies abroad, and in addition, their careers in a great way strive to build with all their might. Naturally, among the countries they want to visit, the fact that English is at the level of the national language is also a priority for them to learn and speak English at a high level.

DISCUSSION

In many vernacular medium schools, teacher gives the important questions and answers to the students for their examination purpose. And for this section, it becomes negligible, since it has been with sets of rules. Even though there are new methods in English language and teaching, still vernacular medium students are getting struggled to get accuracy and fluency in English language. Moreover, there are singular and plural forms that the students have to distinguish and still many forms that have to be learned. If the students do not have grammar mastery, of course they will not be able to produce sentences that grammatically right. Realizing that the grammar, their students have is very weak, so they feel embarrassed when they want to produce English sentences orally. Now, English is an international language. Even technology and working world use English. It is believed that the students want to be the winner in working world competition that is getting tight day by day. This skill will be their plus point in facing the working world. From now on, the students have to try hard to overcome their difficulties to speak English fluently.

RESEARCH RESULT

In this section, we will analyze the information collected during the research process through the application of classroom observation, recordings and the use of oral activities such as simulations, jigsaw, story completion and reporting activities. The techniques used to gather the information will be also described, analyzed and interpreted.

Moreover, we have described in detail the research method. We explained the methods that we will apply for my research, the type of research we selected and the techniques we will use.

CONCLUSION

In the level of school itself, one must know the basic international English four skills. Only then, they can flourish the field they are in. It would be help to one when one enters college or university. Because, school is a place where good thing can be taught and teacher and the management of the regional medium schools have to focus on all the four skills, are important, especially “the speaking skill”. Therefore, a student can focus on all the four skills and a little more concentration can be put on the speaking skill. Whatever points we discussed in the above paragraphs could be followed to get fluent in English Speaking skill.

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